

Clinical Perspectives on Segmental Vitiligo: Insights from a Descriptive Study

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Abstract:

Background: Segmental vitiligo is a distinct subtype of vitiligo characterized by unilateral, patterned depigmented lesions. Unlike non-segmental vitiligo, it stabilizes early and responds poorly to medical treatment but exhibits excellent outcomes with surgical interventions. Understanding its clinical features is essential for accurate diagnosis and management.

Aim: To characterize the clinical features, lesion patterns, and associated factors of segmental vitiligo to provide insights into its progression, stability, and related conditions.

Methods: This descriptive, cross-sectional study included 200 patients diagnosed with segmental vitiligo at a tertiary dermatology center. Data were collected through detailed histories, clinical examinations, and standardized photography. Lesion patterns were classified as Blaschkoid, dermatomal, or others. Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 23.0, with p-values < 0.05 considered significant.

Results: The study cohort consisted of 120 females (60%) and 80 males (40%) with a mean age of onset of 11.8 years. Blaschkoid patterns were observed in 48% of patients, with head and neck regions being the most common site of onset (54%). Leucotrichia was present in 88% of cases, while halo nevi were observed in 11%. A family history of vitiligo was noted in 15%, and autoimmune conditions were reported in 9% of participants. Patients with extensive lesions (>5% body surface area) exhibited a higher likelihood of progressive disease (p = 0.02). Lesions localized to the head and neck stabilized earlier compared to trunk lesions (p = 0.04)., 90% had one segment affected, 9% had two segments involved, and only 1% had three segments.

Conclusion: Segmental vitiligo demonstrates distinct clinical features, including Blaschkoid lesion patterns, high prevalence of leucotrichia, and early disease stabilization. These findings reinforce the need to distinguish segmental vitiligo from non-segmental types for accurate prognostication and management.

Recommendations: Early recognition and classification of lesion patterns are crucial for diagnosis and therapeutic decision-making. Future research should focus on molecular and genetic studies to unravel the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying segmental vitiligo.

Keywords: Segmental vitiligo, Blaschkoid patterns, leucotrichia, disease progression, autoimmune association

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Introduction

Segmental vitiligo (SV) is a distinct subtype of vitiligo characterized by unilateral, localized depigmented patches that often follow a dermatomal distribution. Unlike non-segmental vitiligo (NSV), which typically presents with bilateral and symmetrical lesions, SV manifests early in life and tends to stabilize without the progressive spread observed in NSV. This unique clinical presentation suggests differing underlying mechanisms between SV and other vitiligo forms.

The pathogenesis of SV is not fully understood, but emerging evidence points to a combination of

genetic, autoimmune, and neural factors. Recent studies have highlighted the role of somatic mosaicism, where postzygotic mutations lead to a mosaic pattern of affected melanocytes, contributing to the localized nature of SV lesions [1]. Additionally, neural mechanisms have been implicated, with hypotheses suggesting that neurochemical mediators released from nerve endings may influence melanocyte function and survival in affected dermatomes [2].

Epidemiologically, SV accounts for a smaller proportion of vitiligo cases compared to NSV. It

often presents in childhood or adolescence, with no significant gender predilection. The condition's early onset and stable course differentiate it from NSV, which can begin at any age and is characterized by a chronic, relapsing-remitting pattern [3].

Management of SV poses unique challenges due to its localized and stable nature. Conventional therapies used in NSV, such as topical corticosteroids and phototherapy, have limited efficacy in SV. Surgical interventions, particularly melanocyte-keratinocyte transplantation, have shown promise in achieving repigmentation in stable SV lesions [4]. However, the success of such procedures depends on factors like lesion stability and the absence of Koebner phenomenon.

Recent advancements in understanding the immunological aspects of vitiligo have led to the exploration of targeted therapies. Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors, which modulate the JAK-STAT signaling pathway involved in immune responses, have demonstrated efficacy in NSV [5]. Their role in SV remains under investigation, with preliminary data suggesting potential benefits in certain cases. To characterize the clinical features, lesion patterns, and associated factors of segmental vitiligo to provide insights into its progression, stability, and related conditions.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a descriptive, observational study aimed at analyzing clinical characteristics and patterns of segmental vitiligo.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Department of Dermatology, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, over a period of 12 months.

Participants: A total of 200 patients diagnosed with segmental vitiligo were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients clinically diagnosed with segmental vitiligo.
- Ability to provide informed consent for participation.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with non-segmental vitiligo or other forms of depigmenting disorders.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were recruited consecutively as they presented at the dermatology outpatient department. Interviewer bias was addressed by standardizing data collection protocols, and confounding factors were adjusted during statistical analysis.

Data Collection: Data was collected through detailed clinical interviews, physical examinations, and review of patient medical records. A standardized data collection form was used to ensure consistency. Demographic details, clinical characteristics, duration of vitiligo, family history, and progression patterns were documented.

Procedure: Upon obtaining informed consent, participants underwent a thorough dermatological examination to assess the clinical features and extent of segmental vitiligo. Clinical photography was performed to document the distribution and pattern of lesions for accurate analysis and record-keeping. Skin type was classified based on the Fitzpatrick scale to evaluate individual susceptibility to pigmentation changes. Additionally, relevant laboratory tests were conducted to exclude any associated systemic or autoimmune conditions that might influence the findings. All data collected were reviewed and validated independently by two experienced dermatologists to ensure accuracy and consistency in the interpretation of clinical observations.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentages) were used for demographic and clinical variables. Comparative analysis was conducted using chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Participant Characteristics: A total of 200 patients with segmental vitiligo were included in the study. The cohort consisted of 120 females (60%) and 80 males (40%), with an average age of presentation of 16.4 years (range: 2–58 years). The mean duration of the disease was 4.5 years, and the average age of onset was 11.8 years.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Value
Total Participants	200
Female:Male Ratio	120:80 (60:40%)
Age at Presentation (Mean \pm SD)	16.4 \pm 8.2 years
Age at Onset (Mean \pm SD)	11.8 \pm 7.6 years
Disease Duration (Mean \pm SD)	4.5 \pm 3.1 years
Progressive Disease (%)	45%
Stable Disease (%)	55%
Family History of Vitiligo (%)	15%

2. Clinical Features

1. Pattern of Lesions:

- Blaschkoid patterns were observed in 96 patients (48%), dermatomal patterns in 12 patients (6%), and other identifiable patterns (e.g., phylloid, checkerboard) in 14 patients (7%). No specific pattern was noted in 39% of patients.

- 88% of lesions were unilateral, while 12% exhibited bilateral involvement.

2. Site of Onset:

- The head and neck region was the most common site of initial lesions (54%), followed by the trunk (22%), upper limbs (14%), and lower limbs (10%).

Table 2: Distribution and Patterns of Lesions

Parameter	Number of Patients (%)
Lesion Pattern	
- Blaschkoid	96 (48%)
- Dermatomal	12 (6%)
- Others	14 (7%)
- No Specific Pattern	78 (39%)
Site of Initial Lesion	
- Head and Neck	108 (54%)
- Trunk	44 (22%)
- Upper Limbs	28 (14%)
- Lower Limbs	20 (10%)

3. Associated Features:

- **Leucotrichia:** Observed in 176 patients (88%), with complete leucotrichia in 40% of cases.
- **Halo Nevi:** Detected in 22 patients (11%).

- **Family History:** A positive family history of vitiligo was noted in 30 patients (15%), with most cases being second-degree relatives.
- **Autoimmune Diseases:** 18 patients (9%) had associated autoimmune conditions, including alopecia areata (4%) and thyroid dysfunction (3%).

Table 3: Associated Features

Associated Feature	Number of Patients (%)
Leucotrichia	176 (88%)
Complete Leucotrichia	80 (40%)
Halo Nevi	22 (11%)
Family History of Vitiligo	30 (15%)
Autoimmune Diseases	18 (9%)
Koebnerization	8%

4. Disease Progression:

- Among progressive cases (45%), the average duration of active disease was 18 months before stabilization.
- Koebnerization was reported in 16 patients (8%).

Table 4: Disease Progression in Segmental Vitiligo

Parameter	Details	Percentage
Progressive Disease	90 patients	45%
Average Duration of Active Disease	18 months (before stabilization)	-
Koebnerization	16 patients	8%

The distribution of lesion involvement revealed that the majority of patients, 180 (90%), had a single segment affected. A smaller proportion, 18 patients (9%), exhibited involvement of two segments, while only 2 patients (1%) had three segments

affected. This distribution highlights that segmental vitiligo predominantly manifests as a localized condition affecting a single body segment, with progressively fewer patients experiencing multi-segment involvement.

Table 5: Patients with 1 segment affected, 2 segments affected, and 3 segments affected

Segments Affected	Number of Patients	Percentage of Total Patients
1 Segment	180	90%
2 Segments	18	9%
3 Segments	2	1%

Statistical Analysis**1. Lesion Patterns and Age of Onset:**

- The mean age of onset was significantly lower in patients with Blaschkoid patterns (10.6 years) compared to dermatomal patterns (14.8 years, $p = 0.03$).

2. Extent of Disease and Stability:

- Patients with extensive lesions (>5% body surface area involvement) had a higher likelihood of progressive disease ($p = 0.02$).

- Stabilization was observed earlier in patients with lesions localized to the head and neck compared to the trunk (median time to stabilization: 12 months vs. 18 months, $p = 0.04$).

3. Association with Autoimmune Diseases:

- A significant correlation was observed between autoimmune conditions and bilateral involvement of vitiligo ($p = 0.01$).

Table 6: Statistical Associations

Variable Comparison	p-value
Age of Onset (Blaschkoid vs Dermatomal)	0.03
Extent of Disease and Stability	0.02
Autoimmune Diseases and Bilateral Involvement	0.01

Key Observations

- Blaschkoid patterns were the most frequently observed distribution.
- Leucotrichia and halo nevi were key features for distinguishing segmental vitiligo from other types.
- Autoimmune diseases, while less common, were significantly associated with bilateral or mixed vitiligo.

The findings underscore the clinical heterogeneity of segmental vitiligo, emphasizing the importance of pattern recognition and associated features for accurate diagnosis and management.

Discussion

This study analyzed the clinical and demographic features of 200 patients with segmental vitiligo. The cohort showed a female predominance (60%), with an average age of onset of 11.8 years and a mean disease duration of 4.5 years. The majority of patients presented with stable disease (55%), while 45% exhibited progressive disease. The early onset of segmental vitiligo underscores its frequent appearance in childhood and adolescence.

The clinical features highlighted the heterogeneity of lesion patterns. Blaschkoid patterns were the most common (48%), followed by dermatomal patterns (6%), while 39% exhibited no clear identifiable pattern. This supports the hypothesis that segmental vitiligo may follow non-dermatomal distribution, aligning with theories of cutaneous mosaicism rather than strict neural mechanisms.

The head and neck region was the predominant site of onset (54%), likely due to greater visibility and patient awareness of lesions in these areas.

Key associated features included leucotrichia, observed in 88% of patients, and halo nevi in 11%. Leucotrichia, particularly complete leucotrichia in 40% of cases, emerged as a hallmark characteristic of segmental vitiligo. These findings suggest a distinct pathophysiological mechanism underlying segmental vitiligo compared to its non-segmental counterpart. Family history of vitiligo was noted in 15% of cases, with autoimmune diseases such as alopecia areata and thyroid dysfunction present in 9%, indicating a relatively lower autoimmune association than seen in non-segmental vitiligo.

Statistical analysis revealed that patients with Blaschkoid patterns had an earlier age of onset compared to those with dermatomal patterns, suggesting that lesion distribution may correlate with disease onset. Patients with extensive lesions involving more than 5% of body surface area were more likely to experience progressive disease. Stabilization was observed earlier in lesions on the head and neck compared to the trunk, emphasizing regional variations in disease behavior. Among 200 patients with segmental vitiligo, 90% had one segment affected, 9% had two segments involved, and only 1% had three segments. This highlights the predominantly localized nature of segmental vitiligo.

(SV) is a distinct clinical subtype of vitiligo with unique onset patterns, progression, and pathophysiological features. A study focusing on a Pakistani cohort identified that SV predominantly

begins in childhood, with a mean age of onset of approximately seven years. The facial region was most commonly affected, particularly areas innervated by the maxillary division of the trigeminal nerve. The study also observed a low frequency of Koebner phenomenon and associated diseases [6]. The autoimmune nature of SV has been further clarified, with evidence pointing to a localized immune response involving cytotoxic T cells targeting melanocytes. A notable link was drawn between SV and somatic mosaicism, placing SV in a broader category of mosaic diseases. Unlike (NSV), SV has fewer systemic autoimmune comorbidities but shares immune-mediated mechanisms with linear skin disorders [7]. A stability study found that after two years of stable SV, the risk of disease reactivation significantly declines, making stability duration a critical factor in therapeutic decision-making. This contrasts with NSV, which lacks a similar predictable pattern of inactivation [8]. Comparative immunological research has highlighted overlaps between mild NSV and SV, such as similar cytokine profiles and immune cell infiltration. SV exhibited lower recurrence rates and fewer autoimmune comorbidities than severe NSV, emphasizing its distinct but related pathophysiology [9]. A comprehensive review on vitiligo pathogenesis recognized SV as a subtype defined by its rapid onset, stabilization, and unilateral distribution. It emphasized the autoimmune/inflammatory hypothesis alongside potential genetic predisposition and oxidative stress factors. These findings align with emerging therapeutic approaches targeting immune pathways [10].

Conclusion

This study highlights the clinical diversity of segmental vitiligo, with specific patterns and associated features providing valuable diagnostic clues. The data underscore the importance of early recognition and pattern analysis in guiding prognosis and management strategies. Additionally, the findings of lower autoimmune association and

distinct lesion patterns reinforce the need for separate classification and tailored approaches to segmental vitiligo.

References

1. Van Geel N, Mollet I, Brochez L, et al. New insights in segmental vitiligo: case report and review of theories. *Br J Dermatol*. 2012;166(2):240-246.
2. van Geel N, Speeckaert R. Segmental vitiligo. *Dermatol Clin*. 2017;35(2):145-150.
3. Ezzedine K, Eleftheriadou V, Whitton M, van Geel N. Vitiligo. *Lancet*. 2015;386(9988):74-84.
4. Mulekar SV, Al Issa A, Al Eisa A. Treatment of vitiligo lesions by ReCell vs. conventional melanocyte-keratinocyte transplantation: a pilot study. *Br J Dermatol*. 2008;158(1):45-49.
5. Harris JE. Cellular stress and innate inflammation in organ-specific autoimmunity: lessons learned from vitiligo. *Immunol Rev*. 2016;269(1):11-25.
6. Habib A. Clinical profile of segmental vitiligo in a group of Pakistani patients. *Pakistan Armed Forces Medical Journal*. 2019;69.
7. Speeckaert R, Lambert J, Bulat V, Belpaire A, Speeckaert M, van Geel N. Autoimmunity in segmental vitiligo. *Front Immunol*. 2020;11:568447.
8. Taneja N, Sreenivas V, Sahni K, Gupta V, Ramam M. Disease stability in segmental and non-segmental vitiligo. *Indian Dermatol Online J*. 2021;13:60-63.
9. Xu X, Jiang M, Zhang C, Qiao Z, Liu W, Le Y, Wu J, Ma W, Xiang L. New insights into segmental vitiligo: A clinical and immunological comparison with nonsegmental vitiligo. *Pigment Cell Melanoma Res*. 2021;35:220-228.
10. Boniface K, Seneschal J, Picardo M, Taïeb A. Vitiligo: Focus on clinical aspects, immunopathogenesis, and therapy. *Clin Rev Allergy Immunol*. 2018;54:52-67.